

Mixed Complexes of Copper(II)

NITISH K. ROY* and CHITTA R. SAHA

Department of Chemistry, Indian Institute of Technology, Kharagpur-721 802

Manuscript received 3 October 1983, revised 23 March 1984, accepted 21 July 1984

The complexes of the type $[CuL'L'X]$ or $[CuL'HL'']X_2$ (LH=HATU, 1-amidino-2-thiourea or HNMATU, *N*-methyl-1-amidino-2-thiourea; L'H=HSEATU, *S*-ethyl-1-amidino-2-thiourea; L''= α,α' -dipyridyl/*O*-phenanthroline; X=Cl/Br) have been isolated from methanol medium and characterized mainly from electronic spectra. The five coordinated complexes obtained for HATU and HNMATU contain square pyramidal geometry while HSEATU complexes contain square planar one.

FIVE coordinate copper(II) ion having square pyramidal or trigonal configuration have been reported in some mixed ligand complexes^{1,2}. Copper(II) chelate containing a bidentate (NN) biguanide and α,α' -dipyridyl or *o*-phenanthroline (L'') have a pseudo-octahedral geometry with a CuN_4O_2 chromophore through participation of water molecules³. Tridentate (ONO) iminodiacetic acid and L' also produce pseudo-octahedral copper(II) complexes with a coordinated water molecule⁴. However, copper(II) complexes with biguanide and picolinic acid are square planar⁵. 1-Amidino-2-thiourea (HATU) is quite similar to biguanide and is known to behave both as N, N and S, N donor to copper depending on experimental conditions^{6,7}. Its *N*-methyl derivatives (HNMATU) and *S*-ethyl derivatives (HSEATU), however, behave only as S, N donor and N, N donor, respectively. The present paper reports the donor characteristics of these thioligands and the stereochemistry of copper(II) in its mixed ligand complexes.

R=H, HATU
R=Me, HNMATU

Experimental

Analytical grade reagents and pure distilled solvents were used throughout the work. Metal, halogen and sulphur were determined by classical methods and nitrogen was determined by semi-microanalytical technique. Vibrational and electronic spectral studies, magnetic and conductance measurements were carried out in Beckman IR-12 and Carry 17D, Guoy balance and Philips conductivity bridge, respectively.

Preparation of the complexes :

All the complexes were similarly prepared. The methanolic solution of LH or L'H (50 ml, 0.01 mol) was added⁸ slowly to that of $[CuL''X_2]$ (100 ml, 0.01

mol; X=Cl/Br) with continuous stirring at 0°. The solution was filtered and the filtrate kept in a desiccator for slow evaporation. Fine crystalline compounds obtained, were filtered and dried over fused $CaCl_2$.

Results and Discussion

The complexes are formulated from the analytical data (Table 1). It shows that the ligand HATU HNMATU behave as bidentated monoanion while HSEATU behaves as neutral bidentate. Molar conductance data (Table 1) also support the suggested formula. In the former cases, the conductance values are in the range $16-25 \Omega^{-1} cm^2 mol^{-1}$ while in latter cases the values are $230-250 \Omega^{-1} cm^2 mol^{-1}$ in the aqueous medium. The conductance value in former cases increases with time accompanied by change in colour from brown to green. These may be due to decomposition of the complexes. All the complexes are soluble in aqueous and many organic solvents. However, the solubility is more in the latter cases. The magnetic moment values are in the range 1.73-2.20 B.M. as expected for a single d-electron system.

The infrared spectral (Table 2) of three representative complexes are given for a few important bands. The bands due to N-C-S and C-S of the thioligands show a shift in the HATU (compound no. 3) and HNMATU (compound no. 6) complexes relative to the free ligands. In HSEATU complexes, no such change was observed. The bands at $\sim 500 cm^{-1}$ (M-N) was observed only in all cases, but a new band at $\sim 303 cm^{-1}$ was observed only in HATU and HNMATU complexes. These indicate the presence of SN bonding in these complexes unlike the HSEATU complexes. The appearance of three new peaks at ~ 1036 , ~ 780 and $\sim 772 cm^{-1}$ in the mixed complexes show the presence of bipyridyl or phenanthroline ring.

The electronic spectra of all these complexes in solid state and in solution are almost identical (Table 3). This indicates the non-participation of

* Chemical Laboratory (ER), Geological Survey of India, 27, Chowringee Road, Calcutta-700 016.

TABLE 1—ANALYTICAL, MAGNETIC AND MOLAR CONDUCTANCE DATA

Sl. no.	Compound	Colour	Analysis % ; Found/(Calcd.)				μ_e 300 K B.M.	$\Delta m \Omega^{-1} \text{ cm}^2 \text{ mol}^{-1}$
			M	N	S	halide		
1.	[Cu(ATU)(bipy)Cl]	Light brown	17.21 (17.07)	22.42 (22.59)	8.75 (8.60)	9.39 (9.54)	2.15	18 ^a
2.	[Cu(ATU)(bipy)Br]	Light brown	15.62 (15.48)	20.05 (20.16)	7.88 (7.64)	19.37 (19.28)	2.18	18 ^a
3.	[Cu(ATU)(phen)Cl]	Light brown	16.09 (16.08)	21.11 (21.21)	8.21 (8.08)	8.75 (8.96)	2.20	15 ^a
4.	[Cu(ATU)(phen)Br]	Light brown	14.52 (14.41)	19.01 (19.07)	7.40 (7.26)	18.32 (18.16)	2.18	15 ^a
5.	[Cu(NMATU)(bipy)Cl]	Light brown	16.88 (16.45)	21.67 (21.76)	8.37 (8.29)	9.28 (9.19)	2.01	20 ^a
6.	[Cu(NMATU)(bipy)Br]	Light brown	14.68 (14.75)	19.42 (19.51)	7.39 (7.48)	18.67 (18.58)	2.11	21 ^a
7.	[Cu(NMATU)(phen)Cl]	Light brown	15.42 (15.48)	20.42 (20.48)	7.82 (7.85)	8.72 (8.66)	2.08	23 ^a
8.	[Cu(NMATU)(phen)Br]	Light brown	13.80 (13.86)	18.40 (18.48)	7.50 (7.40)	17.69 (17.60)	2.11	22 ^a
9.	[Cu(SEATU)(bipy)Cl] ₂	Greenish yellow	14.43 (14.58)	19.21 (19.31)	7.41 (7.35)	16.48 (16.32)	2.20	250 ^b
10.	[Cu(SEATU)(bipy)Br] ₂	Greenish yellow	12.18 (12.11)	16.10 (16.08)	6.19 (6.10)	30.92 (30.58)	2.21	265 ^b
11.	[Cu(SEATU)(phen)Cl] ₂	Greenish yellow	13.69 (13.80)	18.15 (18.26)	6.75 (6.66)	15.52 (15.43)	2.20	260 ^b
12.	[Cu(SEATU)(phen)Br] ₂	Greenish yellow	11.51 (11.59)	15.25 (15.32)	5.22 (5.34)	29.30 (29.19)	2.20	250 ^b

a=In methanol ; b= in water.

TABLE 2—INFRARED SPECTRAL BANDS (cm^{-1}) OF THE SELECTED COMPLEXES

Sl. no.	Compounds	dpy(1)	thio-ligand	dpy(2)	dpy(3)	C-S	M-N	M-S
1.	HATU		935			800		
2.	Cu(ATU) ₂ (NN bonded)		930			815	480	
3.	[Cu(ATU) ₂ (bipy)Cl]	1036	890	780	772	715	510 490	335
4.	HNMATU		960			770		340
5.	[Cu(NMATU) ₂]Cl ₂		850			710	460	340
6.	[Cu(NMATU)(bipy)Cl]	1032	870	775	770	725	490 470	330
7.	HSEATU Br					675		
8.	[Cu(SEATU) ₂]Cl ₂					670	485	
9.	[Cu(SEATU)(bipy)Cl] ₂	1045		782	775	672	490 480	

solvent molecules in the coordination. The spectra of HATU and HNMATU complexes are very much different from those of CuL₂ complexes where only one band is observed (Table 3) in the visible region. The mixed complexes show broad peaks at $\sim 13800 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ (having a shoulder on the lower frequency side 13000 cm^{-1}) at $\sim 18000 \text{ cm}^{-1}$, and a high intensity peak at $\sim 23000 \text{ cm}^{-1}$. The low extinction coefficient values of the first two bands suggest d-d transition in an approximate D_{2h} symmetry. The $\sim 23000 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ band is most probably due to L→M transition. The bands at $\sim 13800 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ and $\sim 18000 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ may tentatively be assigned to $d_{xy}, d_{x^2-y^2} \rightarrow d_{z^2-x^2-y^2}$ and $d_{xz}, d_{yz} \rightarrow d_{x^2-y^2}$, respectively. Similar type of spectra have been reported in a number of cases^{9,10}. The geometry around copper for these complexes have been suggested to be square pyramidal. The shoulder at $\sim 13000 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ may be due to non-symmetrical environment around copper atom. The position

of bands depend on halide ion indicating its involvement in the coordination. The peak positions of HNMATU complexes are at higher energy region with respect to HATU. This is expected as HNMATU is slightly a stronger ligand than HATU. The spectra of HSEATU complexes are similar to those of CuL₂ complexes, and like CuL₂, only one band is observed (Table 3). This indicates that there is no change in square planar geometry when one L' is replaced by L''.

From the above discussion it can be said that five coordinate complexes having square pyramidal geometry favour with the ligands HATU and HNMATU while complexes with HSEATU retain square planar geometry. In the former cases the bondings of the thio-ligands occur through both S, N donor atoms while with the latter through N, N donor atoms.

TABLE 3—ELECTRONIC SPECTRAL BANDS (nm)* OF THE COMPLEXES

Compound	Solvent	d_{xy}	$d_{x^2-y^2} \rightarrow d_{x^2+y^2}$	$d_{xz}, d_{yz} \rightarrow d_{x^2-y^2}$	Charge transfer
1. [Cu(ATU)(bipy)Cl]	Solid	13,100 sh	13,760	18,780	24,090
	Methanol	13,070 sh	13,700 (45)	18,700 (105)	24,090
	DMF	13,070 sh	13,700 (47)	18,700 (107)	24,090
2. [Cu(ATU)(bipy)Br]	Solid	13,250 sh	13,950	18,660	23,860
	Methanol	13,170 sh	13,900 (53)	18,600 (101)	22,800
	DMF	13,170 sh	13,900 (51)	18,600 (100)	23,800
3. [Cu(ATU)(phen)Cl]	Solid	13,350 sh	14,100	18,850	24,380
	Methanol	13,350 sh	14,000 (59)	18,800 (107)	24,290
	DMF	13,260 sh	14,000 (51)	18,800 (101)	24,290
4. [Cu(ATU)(phen)Br]	Solid	13,460 sh	14,250	18,950	24,200
	Methanol	13,370 sh	14,200 (49)	18,800 (104)	24,080
	DMF	13,350 sh	14,200 (55)	18,800 (107)	24,080
5. [Cu(NMATU)(bipy)Cl]	Solid	13,210 sh	13,950	19,050	24,295
	Methanol	13,150 sh	13,910 (61)	18,990 (111)	24,290
	DMF	13,150 sh	13,910 (59)	18,900 (105)	24,295
6. [Cu(NMATU)(bipy)Br]	Solid	13,090 sh	13,870	18,990	24,120
	Methanol	13,010 sh	13,850 (63)	18,950 (109)	24,120
	DMF	13,000 sh	13,850 (55)	18,950 (101)	24,120
7. [Cu(NMATU)(phen)Cl]	Solid	13,350 sh	14,120	19,250	24,420
	Methanol	13,300 sh	14,070 (63)	19,180 (95)	24,420
	DMF		14,010 (51)	19,110 (100)	24,420
8. [Cu(NMATU)(phen)Br]	Solid		14,030	19,120	24,290
	Methanol	13,150 sh	14,000 (60)	19,070 (105)	24,290
	DMF		13,980 (55)	19,090 (97)	24,290
9. [Cu(SEATU)(bipy)Cl] ₂	Methanol			19,250 (91)	29,510
	DMF			19,200 (89)	
10. [Cu(SEATU)(bipy)Cl] ₂	Methanol			19,250 (105)	29,470
	DMF			19,200 (101)	
11. [Cu(SEATU)(phen)Cl] ₂	Methanol			19,630 (97)	29,750
	DMF			19,570 (93)	
12. [Cu(SEATU)(phen)Br] ₂	Methanol			19,630 (91)	29,690
	DMF			19,570 (90)	
13. Cu(ATU) ₂ (NN bonded)	Solid			18,460	28,020
14. [Cu(HNMATU) ₂](ClO ₄) ₂	Methanol			18,250 (120)	27,890
15. [Cu(HSEATU) ₂](Cl) ₂	Water			18,690 (101)	28,220

* ϵ values in parenthesis.

References

- B. J. HATHAWAY and D. E. BILLING, *Coord. Chem. Rev.*, 1970, **5**, 143.
- B. J. HATHAWAY and P. G. HODGSON, *J. Inorg. Nucl. Chem.*, 1973, **35**, 4071.
- R. L. DUTTA, D. DE and A. SVAMAL, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1978, **45**, 664.
- R. L. DUTTA, S. P. BANERJEE and D. DE, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1975, **52**, 582.
- R. L. DUTTA and R. K. RAY, *J. Inorg. Nucl. Chem.*, 1979, **41**, 755.
- C. R. SAHA and N. K. ROY, *J. Coord. Chem.*, 1983, **12**, 163.
- N. K. ROY and C. R. SAHA, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 1980, **19**, 839.
- R. E. WILDE, T. K. K. SRINIVASAN and S. N. GHOSH, *J. Inorg. Nucl. Chem.*, 1973, **35**, 1017.
- N. RAY, L. HULETT, R. SHEAHAN and B. HATHAWAY, *Inorg. Nucl. Chem. Lett.*, 1978, **14**, 305.
- R. H. BALUNGI and A. CHAKRABORTY, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1973, **12**, 983.